

Using Sensory Distinctions in Design

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Abstract

One of the main characteristics of being human is having emotions and feelings. Emotions and feelings are playing a major role in many important human activities, such as decision making and planning. They also play a crucial role in design. However, due to our limited neurophysiologic and neuropsychological knowledge, they are often inaccessible to external or third person observation and study. In spite of great advancements in neuroscience, in particular in brain imaging, much of the neural mechanism of our emotions and feelings is still veiled in mystery. While this mystery makes it hard to deal with related problems, we propose a model that can help exploring and changing emotional states in a design setting. This model is based on the work of leading neuroscientist Antonio Damasio and the founders of Neuro-Linguistic Programming (or NLP, a language-based psychotherapeutic approach), Richard Bandler and John Grinder.

Keywords: elicitation, subjective experience, sensory modalities, submodalities.

¹ The second author gratefully acknowledges the support of the NSF grant CNS-0454211 with the CATE Lab at FIU, Miami.

Introduction

Advanced imaging and diagnostic methods, such as electroencephalography (EEG), magnetoencephalography (MEG), functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), positron emission tomography (PET), and optical imaging of intrinsic signals (OIS), provide new insights into the neurological mechanism of complex brain functions in general and emotions in particular (Mather et al., 2004, Panksepp & Gordon 2003). Although finding correlations between emotions, such as sadness or joy, and neurological changes in the brain is an exciting and promising scientific enterprise, studying, eliciting, or evoking complex emotional responses by employing such methods is still beyond our current horizon. Thus, an “objective” or third person observation and study of subjective experience (qualia) is impractical (even if we, like Churchland (1995) and Dennett (1996), believe that this is in principle possible by brushing aside controversial philosophical issues related to the so-called “hard problem of consciousness” (Chalmers, 1996)). On the other hand, first person accounts of subjective experience are unreliable as we are unaware or unable to describe many of our emotional responses. Consequently, elicitation and evaluation methods based on first person accounts, like Protocol Analysis (Ericsson & Simon, 1993) or Self Assessment Manikin (Bradley & Lang, 1994), are constrained and limited. To overcome some of these limitations, we propose the use of so-called “submodality distinctions” to elicit, analyze, and evoke user’s responses in design settings. In addition to first person accounts, submodalities provide clues about the user’s subconscious emotional states. On the other hand, by intentionally changing submodalities we can create desired as well as avoid unwanted emotional states. The proposed approach helps designers to understand and control emotional responses that are essential for making designs efficient and successful (Picard, 1997; Norman, 2004; Minsky, 2005).

Subjective Experience

Antonio Damasio, a neuroscientist and leading authority on emotions, developed a model of neuro-physiological processes defining our emotional states. According to Damasio (1994), at each moment in time our subjective experience is represented by what he calls a sensory ‘image:’ a visual image, that is, an internal ‘picture;’ an auditory image, that is, sounds—discrete or analog; a kinesthetic image, that is, an olfactory, gustatory, or somatosensory image; or a combination of these, called synesthesia. Many people argue that they don’t think in images, but rather in words or abstract symbols. But “most of the words we use in our inner speech,

before speaking or writing a sentence, exist as auditory or visual images in our consciousness. If they did not become images, however fleetingly, they would not be anything we could know. This is true even for those topographically organized representations that are not attended to in the clear light of consciousness, but are activated covertly” (ibid: 106).

When we perceive, we form “images of varied sensory modalities,” called “*perceptual images*,” such as when you see a car on the street (visual), hear a voice next door (auditory), or feel the chair on which you sit (kinesthetic). But when we remember, make plans, or design something we also make “images, regardless of whether they are made up mostly of shapes, colors, movements, tones, or spoken or unspoken words” that called “*recalled images*” (ibid: 96-97). A recalled image *from the past* is, e.g., when you remember the first car you had (visual), your mother’s voice (auditory), or the feel of the cold water when you dipped your toe into the water walking on the beach (kinesthetic), and *from the future*, when you imagine a car that you would like to own (visual), compose a new musical piece (auditory), or imagine how it would feel to shake hands with E.T. (kinesthetic). According to this model, our subjective experience is manifested (consciously or unconsciously) in our sensory systems: visually, auditorily, and kinesthetically (that includes emotions and feelings, as well as taste and smell).

Damasio even requires as an essential condition for having a mind the ability to form internal images and order them in the process we call thought. He explains the great importance of the kinesthetic component of our experience, especially its *physical aspects*, by his “somatic-marker hypothesis.” While processing images, the mind excites “your consciousness in a show too rich for you to encompass fully. Even in this caricature you will recognize the sort of quandary we face most every day. How do you resolve this impasse? How do you sort out the questions inherent in the images before your mind’s eye?” (ibid: 170) You follow your “gut feelings,” or your “feeling or rightness” (ibid: 379), which mark your images and are felt in your body, hence the name “somatic-marker.” The kinesthetic component is continuously present—in form of “*feelings of emotions*” or in form of “*background feelings*.” Emotions are the *changes in body states* triggered by our mind states at any given moment. “Background feelings” correspond to our “body states prevailing *between* emotions” and they contribute to our moods, to our proprioception, interoception (visceral sense)—in general to our “sense of being” (ibid: 150).

Emotions and feeling play in fact a crucial role in life, as “emotions and the host of related reactions that underlie them are part of the basic mechanism of life regulation; feelings also contribute to life regulations, but at a higher level” (Damasio, 2003: 28). These regulations together with other life supporting mechanisms sustain the homeostasis of the organism. The long winding path of human evolution created complex environments as well as complex homeostatic processes:

The entire collection of homeostatic processes governs life moment by moment in every cell of our bodies. This governance is achieved by means of a simple arrangement ... [E]ven in “emotions-proper”—emotions such as sadness, or love, or guilt—the arrangement remains, except that the complexity of the appraisal and response are far greater than with simple reactions from which such emotions were pieced together in evolution.

It is apparent that the continuous attempt at achieving a state of positively regulated life is a deep and defining part of our existence as Spinoza intuited when he described the relentless endeavor (*conatus*) of each being to preserve itself (ibid: 35-36).

Design, as a way to shape our environment, plays a major role in our survival as species or in our drive for self-preservation, the “conatus.”

Modalities

If you ask people to describe their first impression of an everyday design object, like a vase, a phone, or a car, you are likely to get different responses. One might say that “it looks cool,” the other that “it is harmonious,” and the third that “it feels right” indicating different preferred individual modalities. Although sensory experience is simultaneously available to all senses, people attend to various aspects of see-hear-feel experience at different times. Accordingly, the same design might evoke different responses from different people, but also from the same individual depending on the time and circumstances. Design is communication between participants of the design process as well as between designers and users. It is plagued with the same problems as human communication in general. As Reddy (1993: 174) notes, “Human communication will almost always go astray unless real energy is expended.” Part of this energy has to go into making sure (as much as is humanly possible) that words elicit in the receiver the “same” experience as the one intended to by the sender. Thus, it is up to the designer to create intended user’s experience.

Attending to the sense system presupposed in people’s language is based on the assumptions that sensory experience or “the report of the senses” reflects the interaction between body and mind; and that one can attend to communication behavior as a simultaneous manifestation of

sensory experience (Satir, 1967). By carefully attending to (verbal and non-verbal) communicational behavior cues in an ordered manner, one can assess affects and construct new emotional experiences in a design environment. These behavioral cues fit into the general categories of *what* you say, *how* you say it, and *body language* (Satir, 1967; Hale-Haniff & Pasztor, 1999).

Submodalities

“Metaphors are a way of talking about experience” (Gordon, 1978: 9). They help create, modify, and express people’s realities. They help articulate and categorize “raw sensory material” (Glaserfeld, 2002). For example, Le Corbusier (1923) describes his experience by the following metaphor: “A building is like a soap bubble. This bubble is perfect and harmonious if the breath has been evenly distributed from the inside. The exterior is the result of the interior.” Here he chooses words that best express the characteristics, the so-called *submodalities* of his images. Accordingly, Murphy’s (1996) Structural Similarity View might be re-formulated as follows: All domains are represented directly, not metaphorically, and metaphorical language arises when people are trying to express submodalities of one domain using those of the other.

The term *submodalities* refers to subcomponents of the visual, auditory, and kinesthetic modalities (Bandler & MacDonald, 1988; Pasztor, 1998) that are closely related to Damasio’s sensory modalities. Submodalities are distinctions that separate experiences from one another. As such, their significance comes to bear only when we contrast submodalities of images that represent different experiences. *Table 1* lists some of the submodalities for each sensory modality, together with examples of eliciting questions (Bandler & MacDonald, 1988: 46-50). For instance, things that people feel are important tend to be larger and vice versa, things feel more important as they are larger. Important things tend to be in a central position rather than peripheral, hierarchically they tend to be at the top rather than at the bottom, and the images representing them tend to have more density. Submodalities provide us information about the user’s (or designer’s) emotional state, how s/he responds to new objects or environments, either fictive or existing. They are valuable tools to elicit feelings and emotions as well as to instigate desirable ones in a design context.

Table 1: Submodality distinctions and possible questions to elicit them

Modality		Eliciting question
Visual	Location in space	Where in your visual field is the image? More to the left, center or right?
	Distance	How far away is the image? –ask for specific, estimated distance, like: is it about 8-10m?
	Relative size	How big is the picture? –ask for specific, estimated size, like: is it about 10cm x 20cm?
	Color vs. black and white	Is it in color or black and white? Is it full color spectrum? Are the colors vivid or washed out?
	Degree of clarity or focus	Is the image sharp in focus or is it fuzzy?
	Movement within the image	Is it a movie or a still picture? How rapid is the movement: faster or slower than normal?
	Movement of the image	Is the image stable? What direction does it move in? How fast is it moving?
	Detail	Are there foreground and background details? Do you see the details as part of a whole or do you have to shift focus to see them?
	Brightness	In that context, is it brighter or darker than normal?
	Texture	Is the image smooth or rough textured?
	Orientation	Is the picture tilted?
	Associated/dissociated	Do you see scenes or events as if you were there or do you see yourself?
	Border	Is there a border around it or do the edges fuzz out?
Auditory	Location	Do you hear it from the inside or from the outside? Where does the sound/voice originate?
	Pitch	Is it high-pitched or low-pitched? Is the pitch higher or lower than normal?
	Volume	How loud is it?
	Tempo	Is it fast or slow?
	Rhythm	Does it have a beat or a cadence?
	Duration	Is it continuous or intermittent?
	Mono vs. stereo	Do you hear it on one side, both sides, or is the sound all around you?
Kinesthetic	Content	Is it voice, music, or noise?
	Location	Where do you feel it in your body?
	Movement	Is there movement in the sensation? Is the movement continuous or coming in waves?
	Direction	Where does the sensation start? How does it get from the place of origin to the place where you are most aware of it? Is there any change in direction?

Modality		Eliciting question
	Speed	Is it a slow steady progression or does it move in a rush?
	Quality	How would you describe the body sensation: tingling, warm, cold, relaxed, tense, knotted, or diffused?
	Intensity	How strong is the sensation?

Submodalities are distinctions that can “fine-tune” metaphors to *separate* experiences from each other. For example, one of us (Lenart) taught descriptive geometry for years often with frustrating results. To find out why students are having difficulties with this subject, they were asked to describe their mental processes. Here, we compare the experiences of students *A* and *B* facing the same task of proving basic properties of conic sections (that the sum of distances between any point of a conic section and given geometric locations of the plane are constant) visually by using the so-called Dandelin² spheres. The subjects were asked to verbalize their thoughts without drawing pictures or using models.³ Here is *A*’s “mental picture”:

The picture of the cone, the plane, and the two spheres are initially abstract without any physical properties. This is due to the fact that the cone and the plane are infinite, but I also don’t want to specify initially the opening of the cone and the sloping of the plane. As I proceed to narrow down the task, the picture gradually becomes more specific. I choose a specific opening for the cone, like 20-degree, and a certain, let’s say, 30-degree angle for the plane. The result is that the upper part of the cone disappears as it becomes irrelevant. The picture moves closer and becomes bigger but remains abstract. It still has fuzzy boundaries like the contours of a veil in the wind. The picture takes on a 3D line-drawing quality as I try to imagine the curve, in this case an ellipse. As I focus on details such as imagining how the sphere touches the plane, I zoom in further and neglect the rest of the picture. The part I zoom in on becomes clearer and looks like a paper model. However, it is transparent. It is just in front of me about half a meter away. I could touch and manipulate it with my hands if I wanted. When I move to other details, like the lower sphere or the two touching circles, then I move the picture back into its previous position and zoom in on the new details. The picture never has a color, never becomes solid, nor takes on features of a material, like wood

² These are named after G.P. Dandelin, 1794-1847, a French engineer living in Belgium.

³ The proof is based on intersecting an infinite double-cone surface by a plane. Depending on the plane’s position relative to the cone, the section is a circle, an ellipse, a parabola, or a hyperbola (aside from the extreme case when the plane intersects the cone’s tip). In each of these cases we can inscribe two spheres into the cone, such that each sphere touches the surface of the cone in a circle and the plane in a point. This latter point is the focus (or one of the foci) of the conic section. The properties of the conic sections are proved by reasoning about line segments that are obtained by constructing tangents connecting any given point of the conic section with points in which the spheres touch the plane and the cone surface.

or glass. It doesn't move unless I move it back and forth intentionally. I don't feel anxious, or impatient, or anything in this process.

And this is how *B* described her experience:

The scene is sort of grayish and the objects are made of glass. Accordingly it is transparent. The glass is shiny where the light hits the object, but dull otherwise. I don't see high contrasts between the parts nor between the object and the background. It is more like soap bubbles floating around aimlessly in the air. I can see the whole thing, but I can zoom in and focus on certain parts bringing certain details into the foreground. The object is of human size, that means about 1m and it is in front of me at a distance of about 1m. The tilting of the plane is between 30 and 45 degree. The plane is a bit higher than my eye level. The image is standing in an upright position with the cone's axis being vertical. The picture looks artistic, like a modern sculpture. I see the objects in three-dimensional perspective. There is only one picture without a clear background, sound, or smell. However, I imagine of touching it. If I wanted, I could move and turn it. If I grabbed the objects, I imagine they would feel smooth and cool. But I am afraid I would bump into them if I reached out my hands or stepped ahead.

The metaphors or pictures used by these students provide important clues about their submodalities. Visual submodalities, such as location, distance, or size of these geometric objects provide information about the experiences of *A* and *B* and how they try to make sense of this task (e.g. that *A* has more abstract submodalities than *B*, who has more kinesthetic components). Understanding submodalities can reveal comprehension problems or deficiencies and help developing strategies of submodality changes to improve learning. The same applies to design, where the user's experience can be evaluated by eliciting his or her submodalities. For example, the way a (potential) user describes his or her experience with a product mockup may provide invaluable feedback for the designer. In case of more users, submodalities also provide insight of how and why similarities between submodalities occur and whether they are related to similar neurology and/or experiences (backgrounds). However, there are—like with *A* and *B*—also important differences indicating that submodalities play an important role in eliciting and co-constructing meaning.

Constructivist view of submodalities

There is an intricate relationship between emotions and learning. Much of recent research on emotions is related to constructivism. Constructivism is the philosophy of learning (greatly influenced by the work of Piaget and Vygotsky) that has been embraced by psychologists, edu-

cators, and cognitive scientists. Its main appeal is “holistic way of thinking about the nature of learning, quite apart from the methodology of direct instruction, which some call instructivism. Rather than viewing learning as decontextualized, in constructivism it is assumed that learning occurs in whole experiences. Constructivism holds that knowledge does not have a separate existence from the physical nervous system; it cannot exist in some complete form outside the learner and be internalized, stored, and reproduced at some later time” (Marsh, 2006). According to constructivist epistemology, people construct their understanding of the world we live in by reflecting on their own experiences. Each of us generates our own “rules” and “mental models,” which we use to make sense of our experiences. Learning, therefore, is simply the process of adjusting our mental models to accommodate new experiences. Constructivists, in particular in education, have recently become concerned with the “mental representations” that people build in their heads, but they often fail to specify *what exactly these representations are in terms of our full bodily experiences*. For example, von Glasersfeld, one of the founding fathers of Radical Constructivism, refers to mental representations quite vaguely as “conceptions.” But he makes the very important point that

in the constructivist view, “concepts,” “mental representation,” “memories,” “images,” and so on, must not be thought of as static but always as *dynamic*; that is to say, they are not conceived as postcards that can be retrieved from some file, but rather as relatively self-contained programs or production routines that can be called up and run [c.f. Damasio’s (1994) dispositional representations]. Conceptions, then, are produced internally. They are replayed, shelved, or discarded according to their usefulness and applicability in experiential contexts. The more often they turn to be viable, the more solid and reliable they seem. But no amount of usefulness or reliability can alter their internal, conceptual origin. They are not replicas of external originals, simply because no cognitive organism can have access to ‘things-in-themselves’ and thus there are no models to be copied (Glasersfeld, 1987, p. 219).

What does it mean then, from our perspective, when we talk about representations? As mentioned before, according to Damasio (1994: 96-97) we can distinguish *perceptual* images from *recalled* images. Then recalled images of, say, an event X, *represent* X if they are able to produce in the experiencing person a reconstruction of the kind of experience s/he has come to call “X.” Although it is of the same “kind,” the experience that a person has come to call “X” is most of the time different from the experience that a representation of X triggers (Glasersfeld, 1987). In this way a person is able to distinguish “reality” from imagination. However, recalled images are not necessary “faint” as Damasio (1994) claims. For example, Nikola Tesla (1982) describes his powerful visualization processes as follows:

In my boyhood I suffered from a peculiar affliction due to the appearance of images, often accompanied by strong flashes of light, which marred the sight of real objects and interfered with my thought and action. They were pictures of things and scenes which I had already seen, never of those I imagined. When a word was spoken to me the image of the object it designated would present itself vividly to my vision and sometimes I was quite unable to distinguish whether what I saw was tangible or not. This caused me great discomfort and anxiety. ... To give an idea of my distress, suppose that I had witnessed a funeral or some such nerve-racking spectacle. Then, inevitably, in the stillness of night, a vivid picture of the scene could thrust itself before my eyes and persist despite all my effort to banish it. Sometimes it would even remain fixed in space though I pushed my hand through it. (pp. 31-32)

As a “remedy” to his problem, Tesla learned to “make excursions beyond the limits of the small world of which” he had knowledge, and he found that the new places and people he traveled to in his mind “were just as dear” to him “as those in actual life and not a bit less intense in their manifestation.”

While we represent our experiences, as we have seen, in *all* of our senses, traditionally designers are (implicitly) trained to access only the visually oriented conscious mind, and so they often ignore auditory and kinesthetic aspects of experience, thus ignoring communications related to intra-personal, emotional, and non-conscious experience. However, if we intend to use experience in a holistic manner *engaging all of our senses*, we need to also honor other ways of communicating.

The visual system has the property of simultaneity. Images can be panoramic, framed, colored and distant, and one can see it all at one glance. The auditory system is sequential, and the kinesthetic is both. Right now, you can feel your body on the chair and your hand on the paper—all at the same time. But conscious attention will track from one location to another. If we take an emotion like joy—how would you know you feel that? Then from joy to more joy—what would change? Most people feel a wave, a sequence of kinesthetic experiences. They can track where the joy started.

When people compare two things, they compare the submodalities of the (visual, auditory and/or kinesthetic) images they make of these things. For example, if a person is trying to make a decision and looks at a few options, s/he may find that what s/he wants stands out visually because it is more in focus. Similarly, the person can find out how it stands out by the submodalities in his or her *other* modalities. So then the person knows his subjective experience for how s/he *codes* options and how s/he makes decisions. For example, in the above ex-

ample, the students zoomed in on and “materialized” selected parts or geometric objects that they found relevant for the solution by recalling past experiences.

However, people often question whether “this experience is real” or “these submodalities exist at all.” We reply with the basic constructivist presupposition that this is an experience *co-created* between individuals, such as the designer and the user, teacher and student, therapist and client, or researcher and subject, *for some specific intention*. For example, the designer who wants to know whether the user would feel comfortable with a particular device needs to adjust and communicate his or her internal (see-hear-feel) pictures to match—let’s say—the user’s anxiety caused by a particular design feature, like a bright color. The joint intent of the elicitation is to find a satisfactory solution for which the designer has to find submodalities for him- or herself to match or being able to empathize with the user’s anxiety during the elicitation process. We don’t know whether submodalities were there before they were elicited or not, or are “real.” All we know is whether they were *useful for the intended purpose* based on the outcome.

Thus, how we interpret and what we do with submodalities depends on the paradigm we believe in and go by. In fact, the choice of paradigm has far reaching consequences beyond abstract philosophy (Pasztor, 2004). While here we discuss design related aspects, other publications have focused on the overall theme of exploring practical applications of the two (positivist and constructivist) paradigms or thought system’s foundational assumptions and implications in a number of fields of inquiry including cognitive science and psychotherapy (Hale-Haniff & Pasztor 1999); pragmatics (Hale-Haniff & Pasztor 2000); mathematics education (Alacaci & Pasztor 2002, 2003; Pasztor 2003, 2003a, 2003b); women’s studies (Pasztor & Slater 2000; Pasztor 2001); and organizational leadership (Hale-Haniff 2001, 2002).

Attending to all aspects of sensory experience

Traditional (positivist) elicitation methodology privileges auditory-verbal communication, often to the exclusion of other modalities. In contrast, the holistic, constructivist view presupposes that the investigator (designer) should have the potential to attend to all aspects of sensory experience and communication *both* in him- or herself and in the user’s system. In addition to auditory-verbal aspects, visual and kinesthetic experience may also be privileged, with both unconscious (tacit) and conscious communication and perception considered.

In the positivist view, which tends to fragment human experience and emphasize the rational aspects, *emotions* have generally been conceptualized as separate and apart from the rest of

human subjective experience. Most of us have been socialized largely according to positivist thinking, and may tend to think of emotions as sudden and intense experiences that come and go at certain times; something that a sane or balanced person learns to keep under control so that rational thinking and control can prevail. On the other hand, the holistic, constructivist view depicts emotional experience as ongoing, simultaneous with and supportive of the rest of experience.

Defined as changes in body states, emotions occur in concert with other mind-body experience—they are ever-present and manifest themselves in our minds in form of so called “body images.” According to Damasio, (1994: 159-160), “By dint of juxtaposition, body images give to other images a quality of goodness or badness, of pleasure or pain. I see feelings as having a truly privileged status. ... [F]eelings have a say on how the rest of the brain and cognition go about their business.” Body images are of two kinds: “feelings of emotion” and “background feelings,” the latter corresponding to our “body states prevailing between emotions” and contributing to our moods, to our proprioception, interoception (visceral sense)—in general to our “sense of being” (Damasio, 1994: 150).

It is important to note that experience that is kinesthetic to one person is accessible primarily visually to an observer. Thus, learning to detect new categories of sensory experiences in others and us involves enhancing perception of new categories of both kinesthetic and visual experience. By becoming more consciously aware of categories of sensory experience other than auditory-verbal, the designer (or elicitor) is able to enhance his or her ability to accommodate to the user’s experiences.

Beliefs and Values

About the emotional impact of design objects Hekkert (2001) writes: “Products evoke emotions when they touch upon our personal concerns.” These personal concerns are based on our values and beliefs. Values refer to the sense that something *is* or *isn’t* important. The evidence that someone values something is the ‘*difference that makes the difference*’ that they consistently access. People access them when they look at something, an object or a scene—what they notice, what they compare it to; they access it when they make decision—what is important to them, what are the *criteria* that they use that enter into making that decision. Values can be accessed through emotions. For example, when a person is angry, his anger can be used to elicit which important value of that person is being transgressed. One frequent meaning of anger to people is that someone or something is violating an important standard of

theirs. For example, people valuing privacy will angrily reject objects, like surveillance cameras or RFID chip implants (McCullagh, 2003).

Beliefs are assumptions, convictions, rules or expectations about life, people, and ideas. We tend to hold beliefs only about things that matter to us, i.e., we formulate beliefs around what we value. Like values, beliefs or expectations are so deeply embedded in human beings that we are generally unaware of them. A useful way of conceptualizing the *relationship between* beliefs and values is to imagine a sunflower with a center and petals. Beliefs congregate around the center values like petals surrounding the center of a flower. Because beliefs and values are connected together, prioritizing values or deciding *in advance* what is really important to us is a powerful and effective way to streamline thinking and zero in on what really matters—at both belief and value levels.

There is also a relationship among intention, attention, and emotional experience. Behavior—i.e., what and how we say or do—, attention, intention, beliefs, and values constitute a system. This system functions properly only if its subsystems are congruent, i.e., when our behavior, attention, intention, beliefs, and values are in harmony. Such congruence creates “flow” (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990:39) that is essential for any creative activity.

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper is to improve eliciting, assessing, and inducing emotions in a design context. We described here a framework borrowing ideas from neurosciences, in particular from Antonio Damasio, and concepts from Neuro-linguistic Programming, in particular from Richard Bandler and John Grinder. The focus of this paper is eliciting and understanding mental images in the context of design in general and Participatory Design (Schuler & Namioka, 1993) in particular. We propose the use of submodality distinctions to analyze and change the user’s emotional states by co-creating new desired experiences. Submodalities provide us tools to refine mental images and separate individual perceptions. Our approach is closely related to the constructivist learning paradigm, as we believe that we construct our world—including designed worlds—based solely on our experiences. Emotions are expression of our beliefs and values which drive our attentions and are responsible for our intentions. Thus, emotions provide information about belief and value systems that are crucial to the success of any design.

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